

Smart Textile Composites by Co-Braiding of Fiber Optic Sensors

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ABSTRACT: A spatial modulation technique applied to embedded fiber optic sensor for real time monitoring of 3-D braided composites is presented. Several 3-D composite specimens with embedded fiberoptic sensor have been fabricated and tested. Optical fibers were incorporated into the structure during the braiding process. The study shows that; (i) the spatial modulation technique is applicable to optical fibers braided into 3-D composite structures, and (ii) it is preferable to use special geometrical configurations of the embedded optical fiber, to improve the sensor sensitivity and dynamic range.

1. INTRODUCTION

Current research in smart structures involving the use of optical fibers as internal sensors relates perturbations to changes in total intensity of the light signal transmitted through the optical fiber. Other methods involve launching coherent polarized light through an embedded optical fiber and observing the changes in the polarization or phase of the launched signal with the applied external perturbation. In this paper, a novel method is applied; this method depends on the spatial modulation (SM) of optical signals propagating through a multimode fiber. Altering the boundary conditions of an optical fiber induces modal coupling and results in modal power distribution (MPD) modulation (El-Sherif 1988). The Coupled-Mode Theory can be employed for the analysis of the SM modulation. Experimental investigation is accomplished by scanning the far-field pattern at the fiber end.

The application of the spatial modulation technique in optical sensors has been presented in previous work (El-Sherif et al 1990). It has also been successfully tested in embedded sensors, for real-time characterization of smart structures/materials (El-Sherif et al 1993, Kawase et al 1991 and Herczfield et al 1990). The results establish that application of the spatial modulation in multimode fiber is a feasible technique for sensing perturbations in smart structures. Modal power modulation in a multimode fiber is a function of the geometry and the optical properties of the fiber, as well as the light launching conditions. The light launching conditions are the most critical factors for the sensor sensitivity. Deforming the fiber by mechanical stresses or other forms of perturbation results in MPD modulation which can be exploited to sense the applied signals (El-Sherif et al 1990).

In the present work, a novel class of a 3-D braided fabric reinforced composites was selected for the fabrication and testing of the embedded sensor. This selected class of 3-D composite structure was developed and tested in previous work (Ko 1989a). This advanced preforming structural shapes distinguish itself by a high level of through-the-thickness fiber reinforcement which virtually eliminates the problem of delimitation (Ko 1989b). Because there is no plane of lamination, it was found that 3-D braided composites are more capable of damage containment than laminated composites. Therefore, an objective of this study was the application of the developed optical sensor to a 3-D braided composite structures. Certainly, the geometry of 3-D braided composites has a direct influence on the optical sensor sensitivity and the dynamic range.

2. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Three 3-D braided graphite/epoxy composite specimens, with embedded fiber-optic sensor, were fabricated and tested. Braiding was accomplished on a laboratory rectangular-vertical braiding machine. Each of the designed specimens was fabricated to dimensions of 6.5 mm X 13 mm X 150 mm, and used 72 carbon yarns, each yarn containing two strands, and each strand containing 12,000 carbon fibers. During the fabrication process, a step-index silica fiber with a 0.24 numerical aperture and core and cladding diameters of 100 μm and 125 μm , respectively, was incorporated into each braided three dimensional structure. The optical fibers were incorporated with the carbon fibers during the braiding process in one of the three configurations; (a) co-braiding (in 3-D) with the carbon fibers, (b) linear placement; close to the surface and parallel to the axis, and (c) linear placement, into the center axis of the specimen. Following braiding, the 3-D fabric preforms were consolidated with a thermoset epoxy resin using compression molding as shown in figure 1. The

fiber end faces were carefully prepared for high quality flatness and smoothness to improve selective excitation of the propagating modes.

Each of the three specimens was tested under quantifiable applied stresses using the experimental set-up shown in figure 2. The light launching angle used during the experimental investigations was 10 degrees off-axis. This launching condition was used to excite a limited group of higher order modes (which are more sensitive to external perturbations than lower order modes). External stresses were applied on the upper surface of the specimen in the form of a point compression load. The applied stress was measured by a resistive strain gauge (RSG) positioned under the specimen. The effect of the applied stresses on modal power distributions (MPDs) were predicted by scanning the far-field pattern. The MPDs and total intensities were performed using the CCD camera and the data acquisition system shown in figure 2, for the unstressed condition and the stressed conditions. Several measurements were taken while the stress is being increased on the specimen.

It was clear that the sensitivity of the embedded sensor is strongly dependent on the modal structure of the fiber and on the mechanical behavior of the materials surrounding it.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results on testing of the first specimen having a co-braided optical fiber is presented in figure 3. This figure shows, the normalized output intensity profile of the far-field pattern vs. the scanning angle, at different stress levels. Recall, that for this set of curves the light was coupled into the fiber at 10.0° off-axis. However, the MPD with no applied stress (initial state), curve *a*, peaks near 9.5°. This shift from 10.0° to 9.5° is due to mechanical tolerance and tilting of the fiber end faces. For this 3-D specimen, the optical fiber is not oriented on any one specific plane, but it is woven in a three dimensional helical path. The fact that the modal structure was obtained for this orientation shows that the optical fiber is capable of transmitting a light signal following the 3-D braiding operation. The MPD profiles shown in figure 3, occurred when the stresses are applied to a portion of the specimen having the optical fiber close to the surface. Other profiles were performed at locations where the optical fiber was not near the surface and the sensor shows less sensitivity.

In the presence of a weak stress (25 psi) applied to the embedded sensor, a reasonable induced change in the MPD is detected as shown in the curve *b*. This shows that the sensitivity of the sensor is remarkable. As the applied stress is increased (from 25 psi to 30 and 40 psi), considerable rearrangement of the modal power is shown. This can be seen in curves *c* and *d*. Each of these stresses causes an inter-modal coupling leading to a modal power redistribution which is broadened toward the center of the fiber, reflecting a transfer of power to lower-order modes. For higher stresses, the device becomes more responsive, showing more power transferred to the lower order modes as shown in curve *e* (corresponding to 55 psi). As the applied stress is increased, the MPD becomes nearly flat with a mild peak at 0.0°, as shown for stress levels 70 and 85 psi (seen in curves *f* and *g*). However, the change in the total output power at all of these stress levels is still negligible.

Further increase of applied stress (from 85 to 100 psi) results in small optical loss and decrease of the

Figure 1. Shows a smart structure sample with impregnating mold.

Figure 2. The general block diagram of the developed characterization method, where (a) the modal launcher is an optical source or array of sources used to excite a limited group of modes within the optical fiber, (b) the modal perturber is the embedded fiberoptic sensor under test, (c) the modal analyzer is the detection system of the modal power positioned at the output end of the optical fiber. All are under computer control.

total throughput. This indicates that measurements on modal power distribution are much more sensitive than total intensity modulation for this type of application.

For a simple approach and cost effective sensor configuration a CCD camera can be replaced by a number of photodetectors. These detectors can be coupled to simple biasing and signal processing circuits to indicate the spatial variation in the optical signal.

The same test procedure was repeated for the other two specimens (one with an embedded optical fiber oriented straight, parallel to the axis and close to the surface and the other straight into the center axis of the specimen). Similar results were obtained for the sensor oriented near to the surface; however, the other one showed much less sensitivity. These experimental results are in agreement with the theoretical modeling, recently performed by Lei et al (1992) for the analysis of the designed smart structure.

A modified finite element analysis was used to study the stress distribution within the smart structure. This analysis will guide the placement of the fiber in the structure.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The experimental investigation shows that fiber optic sensors can be incorporated into 3-D smart structures during the automatic fabrication process (El-Sherif et al, 1993). Based on the results obtained, it was shown that; (i) the spatial modulation technique is applicable to optical fibers braided into 3-D composite structures, and (ii) to improve the sensor sensitivity and dynamic range, it is preferred to use special embedded optical fiber geometrical configurations.

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Figure 3. The normalized intensity profile of the far-field pattern versus the scanning angle, measured from the center, at different stress levels, for the specimen of 3-D woven optical fiber.